

Original article

Assessing the Pathogenicity of *Fusarium solani* on Tomato Seedlings

Zainap Hasan

Department of Botany, Faculty of Science, University of Omar Al-Mukhtar, Al-Bayda -Libya

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Corresponding Email. zainap.abdulkarem@omu.edu.ly

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ABSTRACT

Fusarium species is a common pathogen of post-harvest diseases that cause rotting of tomatoes and other perishable vegetables. The objectives of this study were to determine the diversity of Fusarium species isolated from infected tomato plants, identify the causative organisms using phenotypic characteristics and verify the Fusarium solani pathogenicity of tomato plant based on pathogenicity testing. Potato dextrose agar (PDA) media were used to determine the phenotype of Fusarium isolates with emphasis on characteristics of macroconidial and microconidial shapes and sizes, colony characteristics, growth rates, homogeneous cells, and chlamydospores. A total of 15 Fusarium isolates were obtained. Four isolates were identified as Fusarium solani then tested for pathogenicity. All tested Fusarium isolates were pathogenic to tomato plants with different levels of severity. Uninoculated controls showed no symptoms of root rot. F19 isolate was the most virulent with a DSI of 47.5%, while the least were F7, F22 and F11 isolates with a DSI of 42.5%, 37.5%, 35% respectively. The potential mycotoxin production of these pathogenic isolates in tomato plants can cause health problems when consumed.

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INTRODUCTION

Tomatoes (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) are one of the most cultivated and consumed vegetables throughout the world. Fresh tomatoes or their products are rich in healthy nutritional components, as they are good sources of lycopene, vitamin C, vitamin E, folate, flavonoids, and potassium [1]. However, tomato crops are usually exposed to many pathogens, including diseases caused by the *Fusarium* fungus. *Fusarium* species are considered pathogens that cause severe losses to both greenhouse and field crops in tomato farm areas around the world [2].

Fusarium solani is one of the most important soil-borne fungal pathogens, causing suppressive symptoms and root rot diseases of many crops and vegetables including tomatoes [3]. As development of *Fusarium solani* root rot is more rapid after rain, and the disease affects all growth stages [4]. Hence, the objectives of the present study are to identify the *Fusarium* species associated with *Fusarium* root rot in tomato based on phenotypic, biological and to examine the pathogenicity phenotypes of fungal isolates.

METHODS

Fusarium isolates

Samples of tomato with *Fusarium* root rot symptoms were isolated from naturally infected tomato plants grown on a commercial scale in a greenhouse. The samples were surface sterilized in 10% sodium hypochlorite solution and washed in sterile distilled water for 2 min, then placed on potato dextrose agar (PDA) to obtain pure cultures. Morphological

characterization was performed for identification according to the characters described by Leslie and Summerell (2006). Where that was for identification of microconidial and macroconidial shapes and septation, colony colour, growth and pigmentation on PDA and presence or absence of chlamydospores.

Pathogenicity test

Seeds of tomato plants were surface sterilized by soaking them in a 20% solution of sodium hypochlorite for 10 min. Seeds were washed 3 times with sterilized distilled water for 5 min. then soaked in a conidial suspension (1×10^5 CFU/ml) of each isolate for 10 min and then transplanted into a pot containing mixed soil (sandy: loam). For control, the seeds washed and soaked in distil water prior to transplanting served as a control.

Plants were maintained for 45 days in a green house. Relative plant infections caused by the fungi were measured after 45 days from cultivation and data were expressed as follow:

$$\% \text{ Survival (after 45 days)} = \frac{\text{No. of survival plants}}{\text{Total of no. of plants}} \times 100$$

Disease symptoms - extensive root rot, wilting, severe stunting and necrosis with premature defoliation often resulting in plants dying.

Disease severity index (DSI) was calculated using the following formula [5]:

$$\text{Disease severity index (DSI)} = \frac{\text{Sum of individual plant}}{\text{Number of tomato plant assessed} \times \text{Maximum disease score}} \times 100$$

A rating scale was employed to assess the incidence and severity of the disease

0 Seed germinated, no symptoms of wilt.

1 Seed germinated, 1-24% of leaves showing slight chlorosis.

2 Seed germinated, abnormal growth with 25-49% of leaves showing chlorosis and/or curvature.

3 Seed germinated, abnormal growth with 50-74% of leaves wilting, chlorosis and/or limited necrosis.

4 Seed not germinated or seed germinated with $\geq 75\%$ of the leaves showing a wilt symptom.

Data analysis

The DSI data was then analyzed using Friedman test of the non-parametric test of SPSS program at $p < 0.05$ in order to compare the variation of the DSI distribution among the isolates.

RESULTS

15 isolates were identified as *Fusarium* spp. based on the morphology of their colonies using the *Fusarium* synoptic keys for species identification of Leslie and Summerell [6], 4 isolates showed typical morphological markers for *F. solani*.

Pathogenicity test

Four Fungal isolates of *F. solani* were that obtained from infected tomato plants. Where significant reduction in germination of infected seeds were recorded when compared with healthy control. Pathogenicity of *F. solani* isolates were evaluated on tomato plants. Inoculated plants were left to grow for 45 days after transplanting. The plants were examined for the severity of infections caused by the fungi based on disease assessment and the averages were recorded. tomato seedling mortality due to *Fusarium* inoculation was low However, significant differences ($p < 0.05$) were found among different isolates for the other measured parameters, including seedling foliar symptom, root rot symptom, fresh plant weight, fresh root weight, dry plant weight and dry root weight (Table 1). When all parameters were collected, isolates were ranked as to their relative virulence on inoculated seedlings. All pathogen-infected tomato plants grew less vigorously compared to control. When fresh plant weight was used as a disease parameter F19 was more effective in reducing fresh and dry plant weight than other pathogens. Generally, all pathogens affected dry root weight comparing to control. Where F19 affected foliar symptom severity, fresh plant and root weights and dry plant and root weights more than other. While F11 was the least virulent pathogen, all pathogens similarly affected root rot severity (Table 1).

Table 1. Disease indices of tomato plants inoculated with investigated isolates of *Fusarium solani* under greenhouse conditions after 45 days of sowing.

Treatments	Mean Length		Mean dry-weight		Mean wet-weight		Disease index (DI)%	Survival plants%
	Shoot	Root	shoot	Root	shoot	Root		
Control	60.66	10	1.55	0.028	10.07	0.44	0	100
F11	55.00	7.82	1.51	0.021	9.43	0.25	35	90
F7	49.00	6.16	0.80	0.013	6.41	0.19	42.5	70
F22	49.66	4.53	0.76	0.013	7.31	0.18	37.5	80
F19	46.33	6.66	0.45	0.011	5.89	0.18	47.5	70

DISCUSSION

This study was to identify pathogenic *Fusarium* species to tomato plants. Pathogenicity test showed that two isolates of *Fusarium solani* were highly pathogenic, whereas others were found to be less pathogenic. These results corresponded to Abiala [7] where they isolated 26 *Fusarium* species morphologically identified as *F. solani* (FS1, FS9, FS10, FS17, FS21 and FS26), where they found the strains FS17, FS21 and FS26 significantly inhibited germination of tomato seed, while FS17, FS21 and FS26 significantly reduced root and shoot total in the tomato plant. Previous study [8] reported that all pathogens under study affected the severity of root rot. Whereas *F. oxysporum* was the least dangerous among the studied fungi, affecting the severity of disease symptoms and both the weights of fresh roots and plants, and the weights of dry roots and plants. *R. solani*, *M. phaseolina*, and *F. solani* is similarly high virulent when these parameters are used.

Our results were consistent with earlier study [9] experience on isolating *Fusarium solani* from infected tomato plants where 27 isolates were tested for pathogenicity test then all the tested *Fusarium* isolates were pathogenic on tomatoes with different severity levels. The pathogenicity tests were performed on tomato of 20 plants for 60 days in a growth chamber with at 23 to 26 C. It was observed that the plants grown in the greenhouse showed the same symptoms that were observed on the infected plants in the field [10].

CONCLUSION

The results of this study provided that all of the isolates of were pathogenic on tomato plants. As a result, we recommend to evaluate the pathogenic effects of *F. solani* isolates on various tomato cultivars in Libya.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no financial, personal, or professional conflicts of interest to declare.

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تقييم القدرة الامراضية لفطر *Fusarium solani* على شتلات الطماطم

زينب افكيرين

قسم النبات ، كلية العلوم ، جامعة عمر المختار، البيضاء ، ليبيا

المستخلص

تعد أنواع الفيوزاريوم أحد مسببات الأمراض الشائعة لأمراض ما بعد الحصاد التي تسبب تعفن الطماطم والخضروات الأخرى . كانت أهداف هذه الدراسة هي تحديد تنوع عزلات الفيوزاريوم المعزولة من نباتات الطماطم المصابة، وتحديد العزلات المسببة لمرض تعفن الجذر باستخدام الخصائص المظهرية. تم استخدام أوساط اجار دكستروز البطاطس لتحديد المستعمرة، ومعدلات النمو، والخلايا المتجانسة والجراثيم الكلاميديا. تم الحصول على اجمالي 15 عزله من الفيوزاريوم. تم تشخيص اربع عزلات منها على انها فيوزاريوم سولاني ثم تم اختبار قدرتها الامراضية باستخدام اختبار الامراضية. فكانت جميع عزلات الفيوزاريوم المختبرة مسببة للأمراض لنباتات الطماطم بمستويات مختلفة من الشدة. ولم تظهر الضوابط غير الملقحة اي أعراض لعفن الجذور، حيث كانت عزلة F19 هي الأكثر خطوره حيث بلغ مؤشر DSI 47% ، بينما كانت العزلات الأقل F7، F22، F11 بمؤشر DSI 42.5%، 37.5%، 35% على التوالي. حيث يمكن ان يسبب انتاج السموم الفطرية المحتملة لهذه العزلات مشاكل صحية عند استهلاكها.

الكلمات الدالة. مؤشر شدة المرض - فيوزاريوم سولاني - شتلات الطماطم